

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF
VALSARTAN BY RP-HPLC****M.D. Kaviyarasu¹, Dr.P.D. Gokulan*, Dr. K.L. Senthilkumar³**¹M. Pharmacy student at Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri.²HOD Dept of Pharmaceutical Analysis Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy Dharmapuri.³Principal, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya college of pharmacy Dharmapuri.**Abstract:**

A simple, precise, accurate, and environmentally friendly RP-HPLC method was developed and validated for the determination of Valsartan in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. Chromatographic separation was achieved using an Inertsil ODS C8 (100 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) column with a mobile phase consisting of acetonitrile and potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 6.1) in a 30:70 v/v ratio. The flow rate was maintained at 1.5 mL/min, detection was carried out at 247 nm, and the column temperature was kept at 27 °C. The retention time of Valsartan was found to be 4.705 min. The method showed excellent linearity (25–125 μg/mL) with a correlation coefficient of 0.9999, precision with %RSD below 0.5%, and recovery of 99.69%. The LOD and LOQ values were 1.468 μg/mL and 4.45 μg/mL, respectively. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines and successfully applied to commercial tablet dosage forms, proving its suitability for routine quality control analysis.

KEY WORDS: Method development, RP-HPLC, Valsartan, Method validation.**Corresponding author:****Dr.P.D. Gokulan, M.Pharm., Ph.D.,**

HOD Dept of Pharmaceutical Analysis

Sri Vijay Vidyalaya college of pharmacy Dharmapuri.

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Please cite this article in press **P.D. Gokulan et al., Method Development And Validation Of Valsartan By Rp-Hplc, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(10).**

INTRODUCTION:

Pharmaceutical analysis plays a vital role in drug discovery, development, and quality assurance by identifying, characterizing, and quantifying active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) in bulk and dosage forms. Among analytical techniques, high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) has emerged as a robust tool for pharmaceutical quality control due to its sensitivity, reproducibility, and ability to separate complex mixtures.

Valsartan, a potent angiotensin II receptor blocker (ARB), is widely prescribed for the treatment of hypertension and heart failure. It acts by blocking AT1 receptors, resulting in vasodilation and reduced aldosterone secretion. The drug is official in IP, BP, and USP. Several analytical methods have been reported, but many involve organic solvent-rich mobile phases that are less eco-friendly. Hence, there is a need for a simple, reliable, and green RP-

HPLC method for the quantification of valsartan in bulk and tablets.

The objective of this study was to develop and validate an eco-friendly RP-HPLC method for valsartan estimation as per ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines and to apply it for routine pharmaceutical analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and Reagents

- Valsartan gift sample (purity 98.8%)
- Marketed formulation: *Diovan* tablets (label claim: 40/80 mg valsartan)
- Acetonitrile (HPLC grade, Sigma Aldrich)
- Orthophosphoric acid (HPLC grade, NICE)
- Potassium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate (HPLC grade, NICE)
- Milli-Q water

Instrumentation

The analysis was carried out using a Waters HPLC system with quaternary pump, UV-Visible detector, column oven, and autosampler, controlled through Empower 2 software. The chromatographic

separation was performed on an Inertsil C8 column (100 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm). A Shimadzu AY220 balance, Opl Biosciences pH meter, sonicator (Sonica 2200 MH), and other class-A glassware were used.

Chromatographic Conditions

- Column: Inertsil ODS C8 (100 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)
- Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: KH₂PO₄ buffer (30:70 v/v, pH 6.1, adjusted with dilute orthophosphoric acid)
- Flow rate: 1.5 mL/min
- Detection wavelength: 247 nm
- Column temperature: 27 °C
- Injection volume: 20 μL

Preparation of Standard and Sample Solutions

- **Standard stock solution:** 100 mg of valsartan dissolved in mobile phase and diluted to 100 mL (1 mg/mL).
- **Working standards:** Diluted to obtain concentrations of 25–150 μg/mL.
- **Sample solution:** Twenty tablets powdered; an amount equivalent to 100 mg valsartan was extracted with mobile phase, filtered (0.45 μm), and diluted to obtain solutions in the linear range.

Validation Parameters

The developed method was validated as per ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines for the following parameters:

- System suitability
- Specificity
- Linearity
- Precision (intra-day and inter-day)
- Accuracy (% recovery)
- Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)
- Robustness
- Ruggedness

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

System Suitability

Valsartan showed a sharp, symmetric peak at a retention time of 4.705 min. Theoretical plates (N), tailing factor (T), and %RSD for peak area met acceptance criteria, confirming system suitability.

TABLE. 1: RESULTS OF SYSTEM SUITABILITY

S.NO	PARAMETERS	RESULTS	ACCEPTANCE LIMIT
1	Theoretical Plate (N)	5474	N>2000
2	Peak Area	3,497,761	RSD ≤ 1%
3	Retention Time (T _R)	4.705	± 2%

Specificity

The method was specific for valsartan, with no interference from excipients or degradation products under acidic, basic, and oxidative stress conditions.

TABLE 2: RESULTS OF SPECIFICITY

Stress Condition	% Degradation	% Recovery
Acid Degradation (0.5N Hydrochloric acid)	1.68%	98.32%
Alkali Degradation 0.025N NaOH	0.39%	99.61%
Thermal Degradation (Heat at 60°C)	0.84%	99.16%

Linearity

The calibration curve was linear in the concentration range of 25–150 µg/mL with correlation coefficient (r^2) =

0.999964. Regression equation: $y = 34547.17x + 13579.53$.

FIGURE 1:LINEARITY CURVE FOR VALSARTAN

TABLE NO:03 RESULTS OF LINEARITY STUDIES OF VALSARTAN BY THE PROPOSED METHOD

REGRESSION PARAMETERS	RESULTS
Regression equation; Slope (b)	34547.17
Intercept (a)	13579.53
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.999964
Standard deviation on intercept (S_a)	0.0195
Standard deviation on slope (S_b)	0.00117
Standard error on estimation (S_e)	0.0186
Limits of Detection (LOD)[µg/ml]	1.468
Limits of Quantification [LOQ][µg/ml]	4.4508

Precision

The %RSD for intra-day and inter-day precision was found to be less than 0.5%, indicating excellent repeatability and reproducibility.

TABLE 04: RESULTS OF METHOD PRECISION BY THE PROPOSED METHOD.

Injection No.	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area
1	4.705	3,468,046
2	4.701	3,502,147
3	4.706	3,494,760
4	4.709	3,498,032
5	4.702	3,513,548
6	4.705	3,510,035
Mean	4.705	3,497,761
± SD	± 0.003	± 16,194
% RSD	0.061	0.462

Accuracy

Recovery studies at 50%, 100%, and 150% levels gave recovery values between 98.91%–100.62%, confirming accuracy.

TABLE NO:05 RESULTS OF RECOVERY STUDIES (ACCURACY) OF VALSARTAN

*Mean of 3 Determinations

Accuracy level in %	Amount of sample(formulation) added in mcg	*Mean amount of recovered	SD	% Recovery	%RSD
50	50	50.31	0.015	100.62	0.030
100	100	99.56	0.541	99.56	0.543
150	150	148.36	0.169	98.91	0.114

LOD and LOQ

LOD and LOQ were calculated as 1.468 µg/mL and 4.45 µg/mL, respectively, indicating method sensitivity.

TABLE NO:06 RESULTS OF LIMITS OF DETECTION AND QUANTIFICATION OF VALSARTAN BY THE PROPOSED METHOD

Compound	LOD	LOQ	Linearity	Corelation Coefficient (r ²)	Residual Std Regression (σ)	Slop Of Regression (s)
Valsartan	1.468	4.4508	25 -150	0.999964	15376.54	34547.17

Robustness and Ruggedness

Deliberate variations in flow rate and column temperature did not significantly affect results, proving robustness. Ruggedness was confirmed by analysis across different analysts and instruments.

TABLE NO:07 RESULTS OF ROBUSTNESS STUDY

Robust conditions		Valsartan			
		Theoretical plates	Asymmetry	RT	Peak Area
Flow rate	1.25 mL/min	8685	1.16	5.611	4184967
	1.75mL/min	7532	1.11	4.216	2983605

Assay of Marketed Formulations

The method was applied to *Diovan* tablets, and the valsartan content was found to be within 98–102% of the labelled claim, complying with pharmacopeial limits.

TABLE NO:08 ANALYSIS OF MARKETED TABLETS

FORMULATION IN MARKET	LABELED AMOUNT (mg)	RECOVERED AMOUNT	% RECOVERY
DIOVAN	80	77.98	97.47

CONCLUSION:

A simple, precise, accurate, and eco-friendly RP-HPLC method was successfully developed and validated for valsartan estimation in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. The method showed excellent linearity, precision, accuracy, and robustness with low LOD and LOQ values. Its environmentally friendly mobile phase composition

and stability-indicating nature make it suitable for routine quality control of valsartan formulations.

REFERENCES:

- <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Sacubitril>
- <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Valsartan>

3. Saleh T, Yaser B, Véronique G. Separation and Quantification of Sacubitril-Valsartan Combination in Tablets by a New Ion-pair HPLC. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2019; 12(3) :1017-1022.
4. Singh S, Topagi K, Damle M. A Validated RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Determination of Ramipril and Valsartan in Pharmaceutical Formulation. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2009; 2 (4): 749-752.
5. Chitlange S et al. A stability-indicating reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography method for the simultaneous determination of ramipril and valsartan in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2008; 1(3):215-217.
6. Choudhari G et al. Simultaneous Spectrophotometric Estimation of Valsartan and Hydrochlorothiazide in Tablet Formulations. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2009; 2 (4):723-726.
7. Singh S, Topagi K, Damle M. A Validated High Performance Thin Layer Chromatographic Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Nebivolol Hydrochloride and Valsartan in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2009; 2 (4): 746-748.
8. Murugan S, Vetrichelvan T. Absorbance Ratio and First Order Derivative Spectroscopic Methods for Simultaneous Determination of Sacubitril and Valsartan in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2019; 12(11): 5251-5254.
9. Shinde S et al. Quantitation of Valsartan in Human Plasma by High Performance Liquid Chromatography with Fluorescence Detection and its Application to Bioequivalence Study. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2009; 2 (3): 487-490.
10. Kumar P et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Valsartan Fast Dissolving Tablets. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2011; 4(3):454-456.
11. Thomas J et al. Design and Characterization of Valsartan Co-Crystals to Improve its Aqueous Solubility and Dissolution Behavior. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2017; 10(1):26-30.
12. Kumar V et al. Formulation and In Vitro Characterization of Valsartan Solid Dispersions. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2009; 2 (3): 502-506.
13. Nayak U et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Multiparticulate Drug Delivery System of Valsartan. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2013; 6(1): 96-104.
14. Patel C, Mishra S, Patel M. Simultaneous Estimation of Sacubitril And Valsartan in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form by Development and Validation of Stability Indicating Chromatographic Method. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2017; 6(7): 1434-1448.